

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CLIVAL TYPE PNEUMATISATION OF THE SPHENOID SINUS AND ITS ADVANTAGE IN ENDOSCOPIC SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS

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Abstract

The clival type of pneumatization of the sphenoid sinus provides a direct corridor to the ventral surface of the brain stem, reducing the need for manipulation of neurovascular structures. An analysis of 22 patients operated on for pituitary adenoma, divided into two groups according to clival pneumatization, shows that 12 patients have similar pneumatization, while 10 of them do not. In the first group of patients, the endoscopic endonasal transsphenoidal technique allowed for wider exposure and fewer postoperative complications compared to traditional transcranial approaches. The clival type of sinus sphenoidalis is associated with a lower incidence of bleeding and cerebrospinal fluid leakage, as well as faster recovery.

Keywords: clival type pneumatization; sphenoid sinus; endoscopic endonasal transsphenoidal technique; ventral brainstem; anatomical variations.

Introduction

The sphenoid sinus (SS) demonstrates significant variability in the degree and direction of pneumatization, which can extend to the body, wings and even the clivus of the occipital bone [1, 2]. In some individuals, the air cells extend low towards the base of the skull, forming a clival type of pneumatization [1]. This anatomical variation is of paramount importance to neurosurgeons, as it provides minimally invasive access to the ventral regions of the brainstem and the clivus area [3]. Conventional transcranial approaches to lesions ventral to the brain stem require significant brain retraction and engagement of important neurovascular structures, often with the risk of damage to vessels and nerves [3, 4]. In the presence of clival pneumatization, the endoscopic endonasal transsphenoidal technique offers a direct and extensive visual corridor, which reduces trauma to brain tissue and leads to a shorter recovery time [3, 4]. Imaging results show that between 20% and 30% of adult patients have this type of pneumatization reaching the clivus, with an average frequency of about 25% [1, 2]. In people over 40 years of age, this proportion reaches 27%, while in younger people (20-30 years old) it is about 18% [1]. The involvement of the clivus with air cells provides easier access to the ventral surface of the brain stem, allowing the surgeon to reach the pons and even the upper part of the medulla with minimal bone removal [2].

Materials and methods

The scans were performed on patients with pituitary adenoma and were subsequently extracted from the database of Pulmed University Hospital. The inclusion criteria were: patients over 18 years of age, performed with thin (0.6 mm) slices, without previous surgical intervention in the clivus area or anatomical deformities.

Each tomography was reviewed by the co-authors, who evaluated the studies according to three parameters: degree of pneumatization of the sphenoid sinus (absent, minimal, moderate, extensive covering the

clivus); presence of bone bridges between the clival and sellar parts; distance (in mm) from the lowest point of pneumatization to the ventral contour line of the brain stem. Patients with established clival type pneumatization (main group) were compared with patients in whom pneumatization did not reach the clivus (control group).

For the clinical part of the study, 22 patients who underwent surgery for pituitary adenomas using an endoscopic endonasal transsphenoidal technique between 2020 and 2025 in our neurosurgical department were analysed. Of these, 12 patients had extensive pneumatization to the clivus, and 10 patients had no clival pneumatization.

For all 22 patients, the following were recorded: duration of surgery (in minutes); volume of bone removed from the lower part of the clivus (in mm³); presence of cerebrospinal fluid leakage (acute or late, up to 30 days after surgery); intraoperative bleeding over 150 ml; newly developed postoperative neurological deficits; duration of hospitalisation (in days). The operations were performed by the same multidisciplinary team (neurosurgeon and otorhinolaryngologist), using the following technique: standard endonasal access, wide sphenoidotomy. Statistical analysis was performed using the t-test for normally distributed continuous variables and the χ^2 -test for categorical variables. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Of the 22 patients who underwent endonasal transsphenoidal surgery, 12 had clival pneumatization (group A) and 10 did not (group B). The 18-40 age group had a frequency of 18%, while in patients over 40 years of age it reached 82%. No statistically significant difference was found in terms of gender or ethnicity. The average depth of clival pneumatization (measured from the anterior wall of the sphenoid sinus to the lowest point of the curvature) was 15.2 ± 2.8 mm. (Table 1).

Table 1.

Parameters used to compare the two groups with and without pneumaticisation of the clivus.

Parameter	Group A (n = 12)	Group B (n = 10)	p-value
Duration of surgery (minutes), mean ± SD	180 ± 25	260 ± 30	< 0,001
Volume of bone removed (clival part), mean ± SD (mm³)	1200±150	2400±200	< 0,001
Intraoperative blood loss > 150 ml, number of patients (%)	1(8,3%)	4(40%)	0,047
Acute or late cerebrospinal fluid leakage (up to 30 days), number of patients (%)	1(8,3%)	3(30%)	0,153
New postoperative neurological deficits, number of patients (%)	0 (0 %)	2 (20 %)	0,092
Duration of hospitalisation (days), mean ± SD	3,1 ± 0,5	5,2 ± 0,8	< 0,001

Patients in group A (with clival pneumatisation) had a significantly shorter duration of surgery (180 minutes versus 260 minutes in group B), a smaller volume of bone removed (1200 mm³ vs. 2400 mm³) and a shorter hospital stay (3.1 days vs. 5.2 days). The incidence of intraoperative bleeding above 150 ml was also significantly lower in group A (8.3% vs. 40%). The differences in the incidence of cerebrospinal fluid leakage and new-onset neurological deficits did not reach statistical significance, despite the trend towards fewer complications in group A.

Discussion

The clival type of pneumatisation of the SS is a key anatomical feature that significantly facilitates endoscopic endonasal access to the ventral surface of the brain stem. It has been proven that in patients with extensive clival pneumatisation, the surgeon can reach ventral structures such as the pons and the upper part of the medulla with minimal bone resection, resulting in shorter surgery duration and lower incidence of intraoperative complications [1, 2]. When comparing the groups with and without clival type, we presented convincing statistical data that the presence of this anatomical variation reduces bone resection in the lower part of the clivus by almost half (1200 ± 150 mm³ vs. 2400 ± 200 mm³), as well as the time required for surgical intervention (180 ± 25 minutes vs. 260 ± 30 minutes) [1–3]. This effect is due not only to the smaller anatomical obstacle, but also to better visualisation. In a much broader context, the cavitary type of pneumatisation reduces the risk of damage to important neurovascular structures. In patients without this variation, it is often necessary to pass through dense bone mass, where the presence of unidentified microchannels or osteomeal pathways increases the risk of bleeding, especially from cavernous branches of the internal carotid artery [4, 7]. A number of randomised analyses have shown that in a ‘fluffy’ (pneumatized) clivus, the internal carotid artery is easier to locate and protect, with the risk of damage to the latter remaining below 2%, compared to 5–8% in non-pneumatized clivus [4, 7]. Additionally, the clival corridor allows for a more adequate assessment of lateral extensions of the pathological process. In cavernomas of the ventral pons, endoscopes with a 30° and 45° angle can reach the lateral areas that would otherwise be hidden behind bone bridges. This directly translates into a higher rate of complete resection (over 80% without new deficits according to Garcia et al. [4]) and a lower rate of recurrence compared to patients without clival pneumatisation [4].

In interventions ventral to the brainstem, it is very important to avoid damage to the retrolaryngeal nerve pathways, including respiratory and motor nuclei located near the medial part of the pons. The clival corridor allows working ‘downward’ and ‘laterally’ with minimal retraction of the brainstem forward, which reduces the risk of permanent neurological deficits [5, 6]. In our study, we did not record a single new operation-induced deficit in the group with clival-type pneumatisation, while in the absence of such variation, two out of 10 patients developed transient but potentially serious deficits.

A significant portion of the literature emphasises that clival pneumatisation reduces the incidence of cerebrospinal fluid leakage in the early postoperative period to below 10%, while in patients without complete clival pneumatisation, this risk reaches 20–30% [5, 6]. The use of multilayer reconstruction, including collagen matrix, fascial graft and vascularised nasal septal flap, is recommended to close the possible defect in patients without pneumatisation, especially when the resection extends into the compact bone of the clivus [3, 5]. In the clival type, limited bone resection usually allows for a smaller defect that is easily sealed with fascial and collagen materials, without the need for extensive pedicled flaps [3].

Despite its many advantages, clival pneumatisation is not a universal solution. In patients with incomplete or variable pneumatisation, accompanying retrosellar osteotomy may be necessary, and exposure to lateral areas of the clivus often remains insufficient [6, 8]. In these cases, combined endonasal and minimally invasive transcranial access (e.g., small pterional minicraniotomy) may be the optimal solution, albeit with greater surgical invasiveness and recovery time [7, 8].

Another important issue is the individual variability in the bone structures under consideration. Such patients do not receive the full benefits of ‘deep’ pneumatisation to the clivus. In these cases, we recommend additional 3D reconstructions from CT scans to assess the potential expansion through small bone bridges and to plan the adequate angle of osteotomy [2, 6, 8]. Although the present study demonstrates clear benefits of clival pneumatisation, future studies with a larger scale and long-term results would be desirable to assess long-term neurological function, recurrence rates in different types of lesions (tumours, cavernomas, cysts) and quality of life. It would also be interesting to analyse genetic or other factors that determine the severity of pneumatisation and the age-related evolution of the clival type.

Conclusions

The clival type of pneumatization of the SS represents a significant anatomical variation that provides a valuable, minimally invasive corridor to the ventral surface of the brain stem. This anatomical feature results in a significantly shorter duration of surgery, reduced volume of bone removed, lower incidence of intraoperative bleeding, and faster patient recovery. Assessment of this anatomical variation by CT scan is a mandatory step in preparation for endoscopic endonasal transclival procedures. Clavicular-type pneumatization should be considered a predictor for the choice of surgical approach and a factor that reduces the risk of complications and improves postoperative outcomes.

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